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PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL INVESTIGATION OF VARIOUS EXTRACTS OF LEAVES OF *KLEINIA GRANDIFLORA*

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ABSTRACT

Phyto medicinal constituents can be derived from any part of the plant like bark, leaves, fruits, flowers, roots, seeds etc. The herbal medicines are becoming more popular because of its inability to cause side effects and cheaper than synthetic drugs. Phytochemical is chemical compounds that occur naturally in plants. The study and analysis of chemical constituents of plants are desirable, not only for the discovery of therapeutic agents, but also for disclosing new resources of such chemical substances. Therefore, it is of interest to investigate the phytochemical analysis of aqueous chloroform, acetone, aqueous ethanolic, ethyl acetate and aqueous extracts of leaves of *Kleinia grandiflora*. Our findings indicate that the presence of phytochemicals such as alkaloids, saponins, tannins, steroids, flavonoids and anthraquinones.

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INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, a traditional Indian medical practice using plant drugs has been successful from very early times in using these natural drugs and preventing or suppressing various tumors with different lines of treatment. In India, people of different ethnic groups inhabiting various terrains, possess their own distinct culture, religious rites, food habit and a rich knowledge of traditional medicine. They practice herbal medicine to cure a variety of diseases. Natural products, especially plants have been used in the treatment of various diseases for thousands of years. Terrestrial plants have been used as medicines in Egypt, China, India and Greece from ancient times and an impressive number of modern drugs have been developed from them. [1].

Scientists all over the world are concentrating on the herbal medicines to boost immune cells of the body against cancer. By understanding the complex synergistic interaction of various constituents of anticancer herbs, the herbal formulations can be designed to attack the cancerous cells without harming normal cells of the body. Medicinal herbs are also significant source of synthetic and herbal drugs. So far, pharmaceutical companies have screened more than 25,000 plants for anti-cancer drugs. This should tell us that looking for single ingredients to attack cancer might be missing the point. Just as cancers are a product of disturbances in the body, so herbs can correct the disturbances as well as control many cancers. Herbal system of medicine has been practiced for thousands of years [2]. Herbal plants or medicinal plants, in various forms, have been used to treat different illness for many hundreds of years across the world. About 70-80% of the world population, particularly in the developing countries, relies on non-conventional medicine in their primary healthcare. India has a rich flora that is widely distributed throughout the country and a large number of Indian medicinal plants are attributed with various pharmacological activities, because of diversified class of phytochemicals, but still, the efficacy of these plants are yet to be scientifically documented [3]. *Kleinia Mill.* is a perennial succulent genus of Asteraceae-Senecioneae. It comprises about 50 species restricted to Madagascar, south tropical and north Africa, the Canary Islands, the Arabian peninsula, Sri Lanka and peninsular India. The genus is easily recognized by the succulent stem, often with tuberous roots, constantly discoid capitula, elongated, narrow, basally little dilated anther collars, style arms with very short to elongated conical appendages, and uniform pappus hairs [4].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of samples

The medicinal plant used for the experiment were leaves of *Kleinia grandiflora* were collected from Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. The parts of the plant materials was identified by botanist.

Preparation of extracts

500 grams of dried leaves of *Kleinia grandiflora* was packed in five separate round bottom flask for sample extraction using solvents namely, Chloroform (70%)-Water (30%) mixture, Acetone, Ethyl Alcohol (70%)-Water (30%) mixture, Ethyl Acetate, and Water. The extraction was conducted by 150 ml of the each solvent mixture for a period of 24 hours. At the end of the extraction the respective solvents were concentrated under reduced pressure and keep it in water bath (at 50°C). Now the extracted experimental solutions were stored in refrigerator.

Phytochemical analysis

The extracts were prepared and analyzed for the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, steroids, flavonoids, anthraquinones, cardiac glycosides and reducing sugars based on the protocols available in the literature [5-10].

Test for alkaloids

The extract of the crude dry leaf powder of each solvent was evaporated to dryness in boiling water bath. The residues were dissolved in 2 N Hydrochloric acids. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was divided into three equal portions. One portion was treated with a few drops of Mayer's reagent, one portion was treated with equal amount of Dragendorff's reagent and the third portion was treated with equal amount of Wagner's reagent respectively. The appearance of creamish precipitate, the orange precipitate and brown precipitate indicated the presence of respective alkaloids.

Test for saponins

About 0.5 g of the plant tuber extract was vigorously shaken with water in a test tube and then heated to boil. Frothing was observed which was taken as a preliminary evidence for the presence of the saponins.

Test for tannins

About 0.5 g of plant tuber extract was added was in 10 ml of water in a test tube and filtered. A few drops of 0.1% ferric chloride was added and observed for brownish green or blue-black coloration.

Test for steroids

2 ml of acetic anhydride was added to 2 ml of plant tuber extract of each sample along with 2 ml sulphuric acid. The colour changed from violet to blue or green in some samples indicating the presence of steroids.

Test for flavonoids

2 ml of extract solution was treated with 1.5 ml of 50% methanol solution. The solution was warmed and metal magnesium was added. To this solution few drops of conc. Hydrochloric acid was added and the red colour was observed for flavonoids and orange colour for flavones.

Test for anthraquinones

About 0.5 g of extract was taken in a dry test tube and 5 ml of chloroform was added and shaken for 5 min. The extract was filtered and the filtrate shaken with equal volume of 10% of ammonia solution. A pink violet or red colour in the ammonical layer indicates the presence of anthraquinones.

Test for cardiac glycosides

0.2 g of extract was dissolved in 1 ml of glacial acetic acid containing 1 drop of ferric chloride solution. This was then under layered with 1ml of concentrated sulphuric acid. A brown ring obtained at the interface indicated the presence of a deoxysugar characteristic of cardioids.

Test for Proteins

To 2ml of protein solution 1ml of 40% NaOH solution and 1 to 2 drops of 1% CuSO₄ solution was added. A violet colour indicated the presence of peptide linkage of the molecule.

Test for Amino Acids

To 2 ml of sample was added to 2 ml of Ninhydrin reagent and kept in water bath for 20 minutes. Appearance of purple colour indicated the presence of amino acids in the sample.

Test for Tri-Terpenoids

5ml of each extract was added to 2ml of chloroform and 3ml of con. H₂SO₄ to form a monolayer of reddish brown coloration of the interface was showed to form positive result for the tri-terpenoids.

Test for Reducing Sugar

To 2 ml of extract 2drops of Molisch's reagent was added and shaken well. 2ml of conc. H₂SO₄ was added on the sides of the test tube. A reddish violet ring appeared at the junction of two layers immediately indicated the presence of carbohydrates.

Table 1 shows the phytochemical analysis of aqueous chloroformic, acetone, aqueous ethanolic, ethyl acetate and aqueous extracts of *Kleinia grandiflora*.

S.no.	Phytoconstituents	Aqueous Chloroform Extract	Acetone Extract	Aqueous Alcohol Extract	Ethyl Extract	Ethyl Acetate Extract	Aqueous Extract
1	Flavonoids	--	++	--	++	--	--
2	Alkaloids	++	--	--	++	--	--
3	Tri-terpenoids	--	--	--	--	--	--
4	Saponins	++	--	--	--	--	++
5	Tannins	++	--	--	++	--	--
6	Reducing sugar	++	--	--	--	--	--
7	Amino acids	--	--	--	--	--	--
8	Anthraquinones	++	--	++	--	--	--
9	Steroids	--	--	--	--	--	++
10	Proteins	--	--	--	--	--	--
11	Cardiac glycosides	++	--	--	--	--	--

“++” : Positive

“--” :Negative

In general, phytochemical constituents are essential for the survival and proper functioning of plants [11]. Table 1 shows the phytochemical constituents of aqueous chloroformic, acetone, aqueous ethanolic, ethyl acetate and aqueous extracts of *Kleinia grandiflora*. The phytochemical screening of the crude extract revealed the presence of flavonoids in acetone and ethyl acetate extract, whereas the tri-terpenoids were absent in all the extracts. The tannins are present in aqueous chloroform and ethyl acetate extracts, whereas absent in remaining. The saponins are present in aqueous chloroform, aqueous extract and remaining extracts were shown absence. The amino acids and proteins was absent in the all extracts. Anthraquinones are positive in the extracts of aqueous chloroform and aqueous ethyl alcohol and acetone, ethyl acetate and aqueous extract shown absence. In steroid analysis aqueous extract shows positive whereas remaining extracts shown negative Alkaloids are present in aqueous chloroform and ethyl acetate absent in acetone, aqueous ethyl alcohol and aqueous extracts. Cardiac glycosides and reducing sugars were present in aqueous chloroform extracts but remaining all the extracts got absence. Phytochemicals provide protection against herbivores, microorganisms and competitors; regulate growth control, pollination, fertilization and rhizosphere environment. The main secondary metabolites present in plants include lignins, flavonoid, phenols, alkaloids, amino acid derivatives, organic acids, terpenoids, steroids and sugar derivatives. Among different phytochemicals, flavonoid exert a wide range of biochemical and pharmacological properties, including

free radical scavenging, inhibitors of lipid peroxidation, antimicrobial, antiviral, antioxidant, antithrombogenic, hepatoprotectivity and nephroprotectivity [12].

CONCLUSION

The phytochemical screening carried out with *Kleinia grandiflora* has revealed the presence of many metabolites which intern contributes to phytochemical and pharmacological activity. Not much has been reported with *Kleinia grandiflora*. The present study portrays that the phytochemicals in *Kleinia grandiflora* may contribute in many significant ways for various studies in a truthful manner to the various activities of the plant.

REFERENCES

1. Balachandran P, Govindarajan R. Cancer- an ayurvedic perspective. Pharmacol Res 2005; 51(1): 19-30.
2. Saxe TG. Toxicity of medicinal herbal preparations. Am Fam Physician. 35(5), 1987,135-142.
3. Trease, GE and Evans, WC..Pharmacognosy, 12th Edn ELBS Publication ,1985.
4. Nordenstam B, Senecioneae. Pp. 208- 241. In: Kadereit, J.W. & Jeffrey, C. (eds.), The Families and Genera of Vascular Plants, vol. 8, Flowering Plants. Eudicots. Asterales. Springer, Berlin. 2007; 235.
5. Adetuyi AO, Popoola AV. Extraction and Dye ability potential studies of colourantinzanthoxylumzanthosxyloides Plant on cotton fabric. J Sci Eng Tech 2001;8 (2): 3291-3299.
6. Trease GE and Evans WC. Pharmacognosy 11th Edn. BrailliarTiridacanbMacmillian Publishers, 1989
7. Sofowora A. Medicinal Plants and Traditional Medicine in West Arica, John Wily and Sons. New York, 1982,256.
8. Salehi-Surmaghi MH, Aynehchi Y, Amin GH., Mahhmoodi Z. Survey of Iranian plants for saponins, alkaloids, flavonoides and tannins. IV, DARU, 1992.
9. Segelman AB, Fransworth NR, Quimbi MD. False negative saponins test results induced by the presence of tannins. Lloydia, 1969.
10. Siddiqui A and Ali M. Practical pharmaceutical chemistry.Ist edition. CBS Publishers and Distributors, New Delhi, 1997.
11. Selvakumar Sivagnanam and Arvind kumar. Preliminary phytochemical analysis of *Tabernaemontana alternifolia*. Int J Pharm Bio Sci 2014; 5 (2) (B): 283 – 287.
12. Havsteen BH. The biochemistry and medical significance of the flavonoids. Pharmacol Ther 2002;96(2-3) : 67-202.

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